
Book Review: Universe, Life, Mind and Reality

The conflict between the various visions of Reality runs through the history of philosophy. What is the relationship between origin of universe, evolution of life and mind? Can we really discover the reality with our limited minds? Can we synthesize these divergent streams? These are the crucial questions of the series of three books written by George Luke:

- Origin of Universe*
- Life and Mind*
- Discovery of Reality*

As a combination it forms a comprehensive treatise on REALITY by George Luke who took voluntary retirement at the age of forty eight to prepare his magnum opus. He is writing these books under sub-title “The Light of System Philosophy”.

System Philosophy is to be distinguished from the systems philosophy or systems view, popularized in the writings of a group of thinkers including mainly David Bohm, Fritjof Capra and Ervin Laszlo. They have followed the empirical approach adopting the process view for articulating that the universe consists of self-organizing systems, which are wholes of interrelated components; these systems have been organized physically at various levels primarily due

to the particle-wave (matter-energy) duality of subatomic phenomena. Obviously the systems philosophy is a physical description of the activity or process of reality, from scientific point of view, without implying existence.

In contrast, System Philosophy is defined here as an integrative thought about the universe as a system of matter and consciousness, where these constituents are in dialectical and productive relation. It effectively shows that things exist by the union of those opposites. This philosophical perspective about real existence involves the synthesis of rational and empirical aspects of knowledge.

The first book -- *Origin of Universe* -- is primarily aimed to address the profound questions of cosmology.

The book starts with the question why the basic questions pertaining to the origin of our universe have not been answered so far. There are controversies in scientific cosmology on account of the mathematical models representing standard model particles, quantum gravity, strings, multiverse etc.

Through System Philosophy, this book innovatively reconciles the conflicts in the doctrines of philosophy of science. Further, it develops a convincing answer to the supreme question: How did universe originate? Moreover, the dilemmas of great physicists like Albert Einstein and Stephen Hawking and also the important cosmological puzzle are resolved.

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The second book - *Life and Mind* - considers the key question about the origin of life and mind. It suggests an innovative thesis of philosophy of biological science, which is an uncharted area so far. System Philosophy logically shows that things exist by the union of opposites. Treating genetic code (information) as non-physical is the vital step to reach the new philosophy about biology. Importantly, life is a system formed by the opposite entities called macromolecule (mainly DNA) and information. This leads to the new System Model of Life and Evolution, which synthesizes the opposite views of science and religion.

The materialist theory of evolution advanced by Charles Darwin is modified in this book radically. Also it would equip us to tackle the problem of missing links in an ingenious way. The age-old problems of mind-body dualism and self-consciousness are solved here through the system model of mind. Also the analysis is extended to develop The System Philosophy of Religion, which effectively provides a new thesis about God.

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The theoretical framework of philosophy is analyzed in the third book *Discovery of Reality* in order to make it efficient for solving the problems of our life. In this comprehensive treatise, author George Luke offers a philosophical perspective of the ultimate reality.

What is the reality or fundamental stuff of the universe? With regard to this age-old question, in western philosophy, there are six worldviews under the main groups of organic worldview, spiritual process worldview, mechanistic world-

view and physical process worldview. These worldviews would logically lead to seven partial theories of reality.

Then, for solving the above controversies, this author discovers a new integrative theory of reality named as System Philosophy. Its key principle: Ultimate Reality is the system of opposite forces called Body and Consciousness, which are represented by X-axis and Y-axis respectively of coordinate geometry. Therefore, reality is like a factory producing worldly things as systems of those opposite components. Further, this book deliberates upon the existence of seven social systems at the global level – like economics, politics, family, religion, etc. – into which human life is divided. Then it reconciles the issues of truth in all branches of knowledge.

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A rank holder in B.Sc. (Mathematics Main) and in M.Sc (Statistics), George Luke was selected in February, 1993 for part-time research in Dept. of Economics at Kariavattam Campus of the University of Kerala. He has an M Phil and has served Reserve Bank of India and National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD) totally for 25 years. George Luke voluntarily retired from NABARD service in 2001 at the age of 48 for academic research. His core area of research is system philosophy and its ramifications for the whole of life and reality.

This trilogy is academically thorough and philosophically thought-provoking. I would recommend this book to every serious thinker. This book should have a place in every academic library.

Gini T.G.

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